

**Surrender or Survival:
*Covid-19 and the Chhaus of Charida, West Bengal***

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Abstract

Several folk communities became the victim of the Covid-19 and its lockdown and the Chhaus of Purulia, West Bengal is not an exception. The Chhaus are the dancing and mask-making community, residing in the village of Charida in Purulia which is the field of this study. The struggle for finances and the efforts to recover their loss with alternate options has placed these mask-makers in a huge mental burden. From the cancellation of dance-shows and fairs within India and abroad to the tourism-influx, as the village was an eco-tourist spot, has put both the mask-makers and the dancers in despair. This article is the result of a study that collected data of 308 mask-makers to understand the challenges faced by this community and their coping strategies. It describes whether these challenges led to 'surrender' or 'survival' against the major threat so far as this community is concerned.

Keywords: Chhau Community, Charida, Purulia, COVID-19, Lockdown.

Introduction

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Charida, a small village of Purulia district of West Bengal, is situated on the lap of undulating hilly tracts of the Ayodhya, interspersed with rice fields, water streams and the Matha forest. She has been declared as the eco-tourist heritage village for her endeavors in the field of art and is renowned for mask-making village in the world. According to the Census of India 2011, Charida has a total population of 2,568 (1,353 males and 1,215 females), across a total number of 546 households involving all castes.

The recognition of the village as an eco-tourist heritage site has also promoted ecosystem and cultural heritage preservation ethos in the local community. She had gradually gone global when the famous craftspersons traveled to the foreign countries to showcase their works and thus popularizing *Chhau*, not only as a dance but also as a community. With Charida's transformation into the UNESCO eco-tourist heritage site, the non-*Sutradhar* (agriculturist) families, besides the 308 traditional mask-making households, have also become enthusiastic in setting up mask-shops to cater to the tourists.

Figure 1 shows three important maps from the specific district-division map of the state of West Bengal followed by the map of specific district of Purulia having the exact location of the village of Charida in the Baghmundi block of the district. The village of Charida is the main area of this study. The map is collected from the official Livestock Atlas of West Bengal, Director of Animal husbandry & Veterinary services.

Figure 1: Location map of the study area

Source: *Livestock Atlas West Bengal, Director of Animal Husbandry & Veterinary Services, West Bengal*

Chhau Dance and the Sutradhars

Today most of us know about the well-known folk dance of the western part of Bengal – *Chhau*. But the dance would not have been gained popularity without the *Chhau* masks. It is an acrobatic martial art-based dance form enlisted in the UNESCO Representative List of Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity in 2010. Traditionally, under the Baghmundi royal patronage, *Chhau* ritualistic performances with variant themes were organized during *Chaitra Parab* and *Shiv Gajan*.¹

The oral narratives attest that the image or idol makers were brought to Purulia from the adjacent district of Bardhaman

and from adjoining states of Bihar and Odisha when the Baghmundi and *bhumij* chieftains ruled in this region. After Charida was declared as the eco-tourism hub, a major shift happened in the themes and sizes of the mask – from large-ones to small decorative. The switch to various designs took place with the production of *kirat-kirati*² and *Kathakali*³ masks.

Ecosystem Resources

The following table (Table 1) illustrates the ecosystem resources and their places of abstraction with their uses in the specific process of mask-making. The data was collected by the author from the field using ethnography as the research methodology with a survey questionnaire based on the specificities.

Table 1: Ecosystem resources required for *Chhau* mask-making

Ecosystem resources	Place of abstraction	Uses
Water	Deep tube wells, wells nearby Rabidh river	Model making
Soil	2 <i>bigha</i> of soil region is located near the Rabidh river	Model making; mixed with water
Hot and arid climate	--	Drying and baking of the mask
Sunlight	--	Drying and baking of the mask

Source: Researcher from field ethnography, 2018-2020

Figure 2: Process of making the *Chhau* mask

Source: Clicked and compiled by author, 2020

Charida, *Chhau* and Covid-19 pandemic: Impact on livelihood

Triguni Sutradhar, the owner of the *Adarsha Mukhosh Ghar*, unfolded their conditions during the COVID-19 induced lockdown. Before 2020, the mask-makers used to see their peak season between October and February, however, the dancers' highest earning period was April and May. When asked about the COVID-19 crisis he said, "*We have no money saved. We have nothing in our hands. What do we do?*"

The nation-wide lockdown declared on March 24, 2020 led to several miseries to the *Chhau* community- both the mask-makers and the dance groups. "*The lockdown left us with huge debt as there was sudden cancellation of more than 50 shows. There was also cancellation of the dance-dress orders,*" said Monoranjan Sutradhar, a mask-maker-cum-dancer.

Figure 3: Mask shops during the lockdown

Source: Dharmendra Sutradhar (Field investigator), 2020

Figure 3 displays the effect of the lockdown in the village of Charida taken by the field investigator, Dharmendra Sutradhar who himself is a mask-maker. During the lockdown period in 2020, he forwarded me these pictures that showed all the workshops were closed and the village main road was also empty.

Furthermore, the traditional dancing session starts between mid-march and mid-April and the performances in

foreign countries begin from late November-March. Each year, these mask-makers take a high amount loan from the money lenders with an interest rate of 50% for their businesses. Banking facilities are all present but the *sutradhars*, being aware of all of them, are still unable to trust the banks. They also invest this money for *Chhau* performances outside of the village or district but this year the story was different.

The pandemic has impacted economic development of the mask-makers. They always buy the resources for the decoration and colouring of the masks in advance and also keep stocks of other natural sources. This habit of stocking has left them with high debt. Post-lockdown, though there was an influx of tourists but it was very low compared to other years.

According to the mask-makers, tourism in this region saw a slow start post-lockdown from November 2020. People engaged in product collection from the forest and selling them at the local or district market, also saw a big hole in their pockets. Another lockdown which started from May 15, 2021 accompanied by the cyclone 'Yaas' led to disruptions in their livelihood.

Coping with COVID-19

With COVID-19 affecting the entire community and its livelihood along with the *Chaitra Parab* being cancelled last year, the *Chhau* mask-makers have transformed hundreds of masks into safety masks. The mask-makers experimented with the designs of the masks keeping in focus the pandemic. Using three layers of cloth material – cotton-fiber-cotton – the mask-makers have introduced new designs considering customers of all age groups. This can be seen in the photograph in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Mask-makers wearing *Chhau* Covid-19 masks

Source: *The Telegraph*, May 17, 2021

Dharmendra Sutradhar (Figure 5) is one of the very few young artists who rely on natural colours to design and decorate masks. The COVID-19 lockdown did not prevent him to explore new designs using nature's services. He also emphasized the usage of traditional method of cleaning- *hathmati* i.e., use of soil as soap to clean hands, which is an essential protocol in preventing the spread of coronavirus infection.

Figure 5: Dharmendra Sutradhar depicting a nature-based mask designed and developed by him

Source: Author, 2019

Due to lockdowns, the artisans witnessed a huge drop in demand of the traditional mask usage as fairs were cancelled. So, they are now making protective masks using paper and cloth that having the imprint of *Chhau* design on them (Figure 6). According to Falguni Sutradhar, the doctors and health officials were examining the ability of these masks to be used as protective face gear. A government official said that they can help the mask-makers to sell their designer masks through *Biswa Bangla Market*.

Figure 6: Falguni Sutradhar with the COVID-19 mask

Source: <https://www.thehindu.com/society/jharkhands-chhau-dancers-and-artisans-take-a-battle-stance-against-covid-19/article31407096.ece>

These same kinds of safety masks have been witnessed by the neighboring state, Jharkhand. Falguni Sutradhar, being the father of such safety masks, resides in this village of Charida, the study area. These masks were sent to Jharkhand as a part of trade. In order to help the artisans and their families, Khadi, in collaboration with UNESCO, gave each of them ₹ 400 per month and basic food items like vegetables, rice and dal during the lockdown.

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Chhau dancer Sambhunath Karmakar and his group choreographed an eight-minute dance-drama titled ‘*Coronasur*’ where COVID-19 was personified as a demon that has affected India and two performers represent social distancing.

Though the caste-based divisions are disappearing and crop cultivation is becoming the second source of income, the mask-makers or *Sutradhars* are not willing to give up their traditional mask-making procedure as their main livelihood.

Due to COVID-19, many *Chhau* groups were forced to migrate in and around Bengal as well as outside Bengal in search of alternative livelihoods once the unlock process started. Furthermore, some of these *sutradhars* are idol-makers and with initiation of the unlock process; those *sutradhars* again started this secondary livelihood of idol-making. Though the campaign for Assembly Elections 2021 brought them back in action, their income remained low. Chinibas Mahato, a *Chhau* dancer, opined, “*Last year, we were left with no shows due to Covid-19. The election campaign had given us a little something to cheer about. We performed at three roadshows for the ruling party in Purulia, Bankura and West Midnapore.*”

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Key Informant Interviews of mask-makers including Dharmendra Sutradhar, Bijay Sutradhar, Monoranjan Sutradhar, Kaberi Dutta, Falguni Sutradhar and Triguni Sutradhar and dancers Shambhunath Karmakar and Chinibas Mahato.

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¹ Chaitra Parab is the spring festival taking place in the month of Bengali month of Chaitra corroborating to April. Gajan is observed to honour Lord Shiva.

² The kirat-kirati masks project episodes from the Indian epics, Mahabharata and Ramayana.

³ Kathakali masks are the replica of facial images from the oldest classical dance forms of South India.